

Comparison of P_s and E_m values reveals that the permselectivity is well reflected in the membrane potential. The membrane selectivity decreases with increase in the concentration of co-ions. Within the pores there will be a diffused ionic atmosphere from the charged wall and thickness of this atmosphere would depend upon the electrolyte concentration. In a very dilute solution in contact with the membrane, the thickness of the atmosphere becomes so great that only cations would be present in the pores and the membrane is only cation permeable (high value of P_s). As the concentration increases, the thickness of the ionic atmosphere decreases and the anions would also be able to enter the pores. It is clear that with very high concentrations the membrane would lose its permselectivity for cations.

(iii) *Mobility of anions(v)*: The apparent mobilities of anions for the membranes under study for lithium, sodium, potassium, magnesium, calcium and barium have been determined. The mobility of anions can be calculated with the help of membrane potential⁷.

The mobility value of anion is influenced by factors such as, (i) the valency of the anions; (ii) the various factors *viz.* the charge on the membrane, porosity of the membrane, the charge and size of the diffusing ion, adsorption and exchange capacity of membrane material which are operative in the movement of anions in the pores; (iii) the chances of entry of anions in the pores and (iv) the mobility of the anions in the free solution.

The clogging of the pores by the adsorbed ions would greatly influence factors (i) and (ii). If the pores are clogged to a large extent, the electrical forces would be playing an important role. Similarly, size of the anions would influence the entry inside the pores. In the free solution and at infinite dilution, the mobilities follow the order⁸ of $SO_4^{2-} > Cl^- > NO_3^-$. But the mobilities calculated from the potential data for anions (having common cation, K^+) at 0.01/0.001M concentration are $Cl^- > NO_3^- > SO_4^{2-}$. The calculated values are quite different from the order of the mobility in the free solutions.

It is observed that the mobilities of the ions increase with increase in concentration of the solution. The results can be explained on the basis of Willis theory⁷. According to this, there would be a diffused ionic atmosphere within pores of the membrane extending from the negatively charged walls, whose thickness would depend upon the concentration of the electrolyte in contact with the membrane. At a certain concentration, an equilibrium would be set up between the fixed ions in the pores and those in the solution in its immediate vicinity. The thickness of the ionic atmosphere would be maximum when the electrolyte solution is very dilute. An increase in ionic atmosphere would lead to greater repulsion, thus, resulting in the lowest value for mobility of anions. On the other hand, with the increase in concentration, the ionic atmosphere decreases resulting in an increase in the mobility values. At still higher concentrations

maximum reduction of ionic atmosphere takes place and from that point onward the membrane effect would almost vanish and the ionic mobility value would approximately be the same as observed in the case of free diffusion.

(iv) *Membrane selectivity*: Membrane potentials have been regarded for a long time a measure of the membrane selectivity. The measurement of ion activity by means of membrane electrodes is most successful in the concentration range over which the membrane behaves as an ideally selective one i.e., $P_s = 1$ and obeys the Nernst's equation. The membrane under investigation is found to be ideally selective for only two electrolytes, *viz.* Na_2SO_4 and K_2SO_4 over a concentration range 0.02 to 0.1M.

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Synthesis of 3-Benzoylhydrazone-2-Indolinones, 1-Methyl-3-Benzoylhydrazone-2-Indolinones and 1-Morpholino/Piperidinomethyl-3-Benzoylhydrazone-2-Indolinones†

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A number of 3-arylimino-2-indolinones and their 1-methyl and 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl analogs were synthesised recently as excystment and cysticidal agents¹⁻³. The present communication describes the synthesis of several 3-benzoylhydrazone-2-indolinones(I), 1-methyl-3-benzoylhydrazone-2-indolinones(II) and 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-benzoylhydrazone-2-indolinones(III).

† Part XVIII of the series of Potential Biologically Active Agents.

TABLE 1—MORPHOLINO/PIPERIDINOMETHYL-3-BENZOYLHYDRAZONO-2-INDOLINONES(III)

Sl.No.	R	R'	X	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	% N Analyses	
							Calcd.	Found
9.	Cl	H	CH ₂	65	191	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ ClN ₄ O ₂	14.12	14.40
10.	Cl	H	O	65	203-4	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₂	14.05	13.80
11.	Cl	OH	CH ₂	75	228-29	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ ClN ₄ O ₃	13.58	13.19
12.	Cl	OH	O	72	170	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₃	13.51	12.95
13.	Br	H	CH ₂	70	178-79	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ BrN ₄ O ₂	12.69	12.31
14.	Br	H	O	75	204	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ BrN ₄ O ₂	12.64	12.27
15.	Br	OH	CH ₂	75	228-30	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ BrN ₄ O ₃	12.24	11.88
16.	Br	OH	O	72	218-20	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ BrN ₄ O ₃	12.19	11.87

I.R. (cm⁻¹): Compound 9, 3160(NH), 2920 (CH₂), 1695 (C=O, ring), 1670 (C=O, hydrazide)

N.M.R (δ): Compound 9, 1.43 (CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.56 (N $\begin{matrix} \text{OH} \\ \diagup \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix}$), 4.43 (N-CH₂-N), 6.9-8.03 (Ar-H), 13.83 (CONH).

Indole-2,3-diones prepared via Sandmeyer reaction⁴ were treated with benzoic acid hydrazides in acid medium for the synthesis of (I). Condensation of 1-methyl-indole-2,3-diones with benzoic acid hydrazides under similar conditions furnished (II). Condensation of (I) with formalin and morpholine/piperidine yielded (III) in good yields. (I) (R''=OH) has two sites for Mannich condensation (position 1 and 3'). But the condensation takes place only at position 1 and not at 3'. This has been ascertained by subjecting (II) (R''=OH) to Mannich reaction. (II) (R''=OH), which is capable of undergoing such reaction at position 3' did not yield any Mannich base, only the starting materials were recovered from the reaction mixture. (I), (II) and (III) have been adequately characterised by means of elemental analyses, infrared and nmr spectral data. The nmr spectrum of compound 9 (Table 1) showed signals at 1.43 (CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.56 (N $\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_2 \\ \diagup \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{matrix}$), 4.43 (N-CH₂-N), 6.9-8.03 (Ar-H) and 13.83 δ (CONH). The signal at 13.83 disappeared on D₂O exchange.

None of these compounds (I, II, III) showed any excystment and cysticidal action against *S. russeli*⁵. It has been observed that these compounds delayed the excystment of cysts for 24 hr. Cysts treated with these compounds excysted after 48 hr while cysts treated with bacterial extract alone excysted after 24 hr.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 Infracord Spectrophotometer in KBr. NMR spectrum was recorded in CDCl₃ on a Varian A60D instrument using TMS as an internal standard.

3-Benzoylhydrazono-2-indolinones (Ia - Id): A mixture of indole-2,3-dione(s) (0.01 mole) and benzoic acid hydrazide (0.01 mole) in 15 ml of ethanol containing one drop of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated solid was filtered and

washed well with ethanol and petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), IR : (Ib) : 3200 (OH, NH), 1720 (C=O, ring), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O, hydrazide).

1-Methyl-3-benzoylhydrazono-2-indolinones (IIa - IIId): A mixture of 1-methylindole-2,3-dione(s) (0.01 mole) and benzoic acid hydrazide (0.01 mole) in 20 ml of ethanol containing 2 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. The solid mass, that separated on cooling was filtered, washed well with ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol to obtain the pure product. IR : (IIId) : 3250 (OH, NH), 1680 (C=O, ring), 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=O, hydrazide).

1-Morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-benzoylhydrazono-2-indolinones (III): (I) (0.01 mole) was suspended in 20 ml of ethanol. The suspension was warmed on a water bath and formalin (2 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) were added to it with vigorous stirring. The whole was thereafter kept overnight at room temperature. The crystalline solid that separated was filtered, washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and finally recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride. A number of (III) thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

	m.p. °C
Ia ; R=H, R''=H, R'=Cl (80%)	> 275
Ib ; R=H, R''=Cl, R'=OH (85%)	> 280
Ic ; R=H, R''=Br, R'=H (85%)	> 260
Id ; R=H, R''=Br, R'=OH (82%)	> 263
IIa ; R=Me, R''=H, R'=H (65%)	179-180
IIb ; R=Me, R''=H, R'=OH (60%)	> 250
IIc ; R=Me, R''=Cl, R'=H (75%)	201-202
IIId ; R=Me, R''=Cl, R'=OH (70%)	> 280

III (X=CH₂, or O)

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Synthesis of Some New 3,5-dimethyl-4-phenylazo-N'-thiocarbamoylpyrazoles

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In order to examine their hypoglycemic activity a series of 4-arylhydrazono-N'-arylthiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones has been synthesised and reported in a separate communication¹. The present report concerns the synthesis of 3,5-dimethyl-4-phenylazo-N'-arylthiocarbamoylpyrazoles(A).

The compounds described here have been synthesised by reacting 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones with different derivatives of phenylthiosemicarbazides. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental, ir and mass spectral studies. The reactivity of 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones was smooth and the products were obtained in good yield. The reactivity followed the expected course, diazonium chloride with electron withdrawing group in position 2 and 4 gave better yields. Colour of compounds ranges from yellow to orange.

Experimental

IR spectra were taken in KBr film on a Beckmann I.R. spectrophotometer. Mass spectral studies were carried out on a Varian Mat-CH-7 mass spectrophotometer. 2,3,4-Pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones were prepared by the reported method².

3,5-Dimethyl-4-phenylazo-N'-thiocarbamoylpyrazoles: 2,3,4-Pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazone (0.004 mol) was dissolved in alcohol (50 ml). A hot solution of phenylthiosemicarbazide (0.004 mol) in alcohol was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hrs. Shining crystals separated out on cooling which were recrystallised from 60% ethyl alcohol. Anal: m.p. 78°. Calculated for C₁₈H₁₇N₅S: N, 20.95%. Found: N, 20.7% $\nu^{(KBr)}$ 1600 cm⁻¹ (-N=N), 3420 cm⁻¹ (-NH), 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=C or C=N) and 830-690 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl) λ_{max} CH₃OH 425 nm for -N=N- grouping, M⁺ at m/e 335.

Other 3,5-dimethyl-4-phenylazo-N'-thiocarbamoylpyrazoles were prepared in the same way by taking suitably substituted phenylthiosemicarbazide and 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-arylhydrazones and their characteristics are compiled in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 3,5-DIMETHYL-4-PHENYLAZO-N'-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYLPIRAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Yield %	m.p. °C
1.	H	C ₆ H ₅	70%	78
2.	2-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	60%	121
3.	3-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	60%	184
4.	4-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	65%	129
5.	2-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	60%	125
6.	4-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	55%	96
7.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	50%	132
8.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	55%	116
9.	2-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	65%	110
10.	3-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	60%	108
11.	4-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	55%	103
12.	2-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	75%	176
13.	4-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	78%	210
14.	4-Br	C ₆ H ₅	65%	120
15.	2,5-(Cl) ₂	C ₆ H ₅	63%	125
16.	H	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65%	85
17.	2-Cl	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60%	118
18.	4-Cl	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	65%	130
19.	2-CH ₃	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60%	113
20.	4-CH ₃	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55%	97
21.	2-OCH ₃	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	50%	137
22.	4-OCH ₃	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55%	160
23.	2-NO ₂	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	70%	148
24.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	55%	200
25.	4-Br	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	60%	125
26.	2,5(Cl) ₂	m-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	67%	124

All the compounds gave consistent nitrogen analysis.

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